

Interaction of Carbon Blacks with Hydroquinone in Aqueous Solution

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Interaction of hydroquinone in aqueous solution with carbon black involves physical adsorption as well as chemisorption of hydroquinone on the surface of the black. There is no evidence for oxidation of hydroquinone to quinone. Physical adsorption seems to be a function of surface area while chemisorption appears to occur at sites occupied by quinonic oxygen resulting in the formation of semi-quinonic structures on the surface. In the case of oxygen-free carbons, as those obtained on outgassing at 1000°, chemisorption occurs probably, at the sites vacated by quinonic groups. The chemisorbed hydroquinone can be recovered to the extent of over 70 per cent, in either case, on treating the carbon with boiling solution of sodium sulphite under reflux.

KING¹ and Bente and Walton² reported aerobic oxidation of hydroquinone in the presence of charcoals. Lur'e et al³. observed a distinct fall in concentration when aqueous solution of hydroquinone was passed through a charcoal column. The hydroquinone, lost in this manner, could be recovered substantially on the leaching of charcoal with sodium sulphite. It appears that no systematic investigation with regard to the exact nature of the reaction or the role of the nature and extent of the carbon surface has been made so far. The problem is of interest from the point of view of probable existence of quinone-hydroquinone systems⁴ on carbon surfaces. The present work was, therefore, undertaken.

Experimental

Materials. A few, well known samples of commercial carbon blacks were used before as well as after outgassing at various temperatures. The combined oxygen evolved as carbon dioxide and carbon monoxide was obtained by outgassing 0.5 g. portion in a resistance tube furnace, the temperature of which was raised gradually to 1200°, and analysing the gases evolved in the manner described before⁵. These values together with specific surface areas (nitrogen, B. E. T.) of the various carbon blacks are given in Table 1.

Procedure. Carbon (1 g. oven dried at 120°) was mixed with 100 ml. of aqueous solution of hydroquinone of a given concentration in a pyrex glass bottle of about 250 ml capacity. The suspension was shaken for a few minutes and then allowed to stand in a thermostat maintained at 35° ($\pm 0.02^\circ$) with occasional shaking. The fall in concentration was estimated, after different intervals of time, by withdrawing an aliquot of the clear supernatant liquid and titrating against standard ceric sulphate. The solution was also checked polarographically (using sulphuric acid as the supporting electrolyte) for the presence of quinone formed, if any, during the reaction. A blank was also run without the addition of carbon black to the solution but no change in the concentration

of hydroquinone was observed even after 48 hr. interval under the conditions of the experiment.

The carbon black, after the reaction, was refluxed with distilled water for 10 hr. to recover physically (reversibly) adsorbed hydroquinone. This subtracted from the total amount removed from the solution gave the amount of hydroquinone chemisorbed by the carbon. The presence of quinone in the refluxate, if any, was also checked polarographically.

Results and Discussion

The results of preliminary experiments showed that maximum value for the adsorption of hydroquinone at 35° could be obtained by keeping 0.4 M solution in contact with carbon for a period of at least 4 hr. The amounts adsorbed and their break-ups into physical (reversible) adsorption and chemisorption, in the case of various carbon blacks are given in Table 1. The amount adsorbed reversibly is larger in each case and appears to be, to some extent, a function of specific surface area of the black. This can be shown by a plot between the two values when most of the points would fit around a straight line. Physical adsorption, therefore, appears to be, more or less, independent of the nature of the surface. This is not the case, however, with the chemisorption of hydroquinone. Spheron-C and Spheron-4, for example, chemisorb nearly the same amount of hydroquinone although they differ widely in their respective surface areas. The role of the nature rather than the magnitude of the surface seems to be more important.

One significant observation that was made in these investigations was that there was no formation of quinone either in the solution or on the surface of any of the carbon blacks. This was found by polarographic examination of the hydroquinone solution left after the reaction as well as that of the refluxate obtained on prolonged boiling of the treated carbons in water under reflux for several hours.

It is seen (Table 1) that colour blacks, which are rich in oxygen, chemisorb more of hydroquinone than either channel or furnace blacks. Graphon, which is essentially free of oxygen, does not chemisorb hydroquinone at all. chemisorbed hydroquinone, however, increase on outgassing up to 700°, in every case, inspite of decline in oxygen content evolved as CO₂ and CO. The values fall slightly thereafter on outgassing at 1000°, when the carbons get essentially freed of oxygen.

TABLE 1—AMOUNTS OF HYDROQUINONE PHYSICALLY ADSORBED AND CHEMISORBED BY VARIOUS CARBON BLACKS ALONG WITH SOME OTHER CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BLACKS

Description of the sample	Oxygen evolved on outgassing at 1200°C as		Surface area (m ² /g)	Amount of hydroquinone adsorbed (g/100g)			
	CO ₂ (g/100g)	CO (g/100g)		Total	Physically adsorbed	Chemisorbed	
Colour blacks	Carbolac	4.75	5.07	839.2	17.05	11.55	5.50
	Mogul-A	1.89	4.23	228.4	9.65	5.80	3.85
	Elf-O	1.18	2.17	171.0	4.95	2.75	2.20
Channel blacks	Spheron-C	0.58	2.00	253.7	7.15	5.50	1.65
	Spheron-6	0.50	2.12	120.0	3.31	1.93	1.38
	Spheron-4	0.55	2.83	152.7	3.85	2.20	1.65
	Spheron-9	0.54	1.93	115.9	4.53	2.06	1.93
Furnace blacks	Vulcan-SC	0.43	0.80	193.0	4.28	3.45	0.83
	Philblack-O	0.21	0.43	79.6	1.93	1.65	0.28
	Philblack-I	0.35	0.63	116.8	2.75	1.65	1.10
	Philblack-A	0.19	0.34	45.8	0.83	0.55	0.28
	Kosmos-40	0.09	0.32	31.2	1.11	0.83	0.28
	Graphon	Nil	Nil	90.0	2.20	2.20	Nil

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF OUTGASSING CARBON BLACKS ON PHYSICAL ADSORPTION AND CHEMISORPTION OF HYDROQUINONE AND SOME OTHER CHARACTERISTICS OF THE BLACKS

Description of the sample	Oxygen evolved on outgassing at 1200°C as:		Surface area (m ² /g)	Amount of hydroquinone physically adsorbed (g/100g)	Amount of hydroquinone chemisorbed (g/100 g)
	CO ₂ (g/100g)	CO (g/100g)			
CARBOLAC					
Original	4.75	5.07	839	11.55	5.50
Outgassed at 400°	2.48	4.98	830	11.60	7.65
Outgassed at 550°	6.73	4.60	815	11.90	8.60
Outgassed at 700°	Nil	3.92	809	12.65	11.00
Outgassed at 1000°	Nil	Nil	760	11.00	10.15
MOGUL-A					
Original	1.89	4.23	228	5.80	3.85
Outgassed at 400°	0.96	4.20	225	5.50	4.95
Outgassed at 550°	0.45	4.00	222	5.35	5.20
Outgassed at 700°	Nil	3.16	218	4.50	5.50
Outgassed at 1000°	Nil	Nil	182	3.50	4.40
SPHERON-C					
Original	0.58	2.00	253	5.50	1.65
Outgassed at 400°	0.36	1.98	248	4.90	2.20
Outgassed at 550°	0.15	1.86	—	5.20	2.60
Outgassed at 700°	Nil	1.60	225	4.15	3.30
Outgassed at 1000°	Nil	Nil	200	3.35	2.50

In order to check the influence of chemisorbed oxygen in further details, three of the carbon blacks, two belonging to colour black variety and one to channel black variety, were outgassed at different temperatures upto 1000° before studying the reaction. The results are given in Table 2 along with other details. It is seen that the values for physically adsorbed hydroquinone change only slightly and may be due to corresponding changes in specific surface area. The values for

Considering the results obtained on outgassing upto 700° only in the first instance, it is observed that this treatment causes progressive elimination of more of CO₂-complex than that of CO-complex. At 700°, the first mentioned complex gets eliminated almost completely while over 70-80 per cent of CO-complex remains intact. It seems probable that chemisorption of hydroquinone occurs at the sites occupied by CO-complex and the extent of interaction increases as the CO₂ complex

gets eliminated. It is now well known that while evolution of carbon dioxide arises from thermal decomposition of carboxylic⁶ or lactonic^{6,7} groups or from certain oxygen structures in which two oxygen atoms are attached to each surface active carbon atom⁸, that of carbon monoxide arises from quinonic and phenolic groups present on the surface⁹. It has also been shown that the action of quinonic groups in improving adsorbability of benzene from vapour¹⁰ or solution phase¹¹ by carbon blacks through the interaction of π electrons of the benzene ring with partial positive charge on the carbonyl carbon atom comes into greater prominence with progressive removal of the polar CO₂-complex. The results of present investigations appear to be in line with the previous findings.

It appears highly likely that hydroquinone gets chemisorbed at the quinonic sites giving rise to semi-quinonic structures, on the surface, represented as

The existence of such structures has been reported by Luvalle and Weissberger^{1,2}.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF TREATING 700° OUTGASSED CARBONS WITH HYDROGEN AT 160° ON THE ADSORPTION OF HYDROQUINONE

Description of the sample	Amount of hydroquinone of physically adsorbed (g/100 g)	Amount of hydroquinone chemisorbed (g/100 g)
Carbolac outgassed at 700°	12.65	11.00
Carbolac outgassed at 700° and treated with hydrogen at 160°	12.40	8.90
Mogul-A outgassed at 700°	4.50	5.50
Mogul-A outgassed at 700° and treated with hydrogen at 160°	4.40	3.85
Spheron-C outgassed at 700°	4.15	3.30
Spheron-C outgassed at 700° and treated with hydrogen at 160°	4.10	2.15

The role of quinonic oxygen in enhancing chemisorption of hydroquinone was checked in two ways. Firstly, the quinonic groups on the surface were reduced partly to hydroquinonic groups by treating 700°-outgassed carbon blacks in a current of hydrogen at 160° for 4 hours^{1,3}. This treatment is known to cause partial reduction of surface quinones into hydroquinones, there being virtually no change in oxygen content. The results of interaction of the reduced carbons with hydroquinone solutions are given in Table 3. It is seen that while there is very little change in the value for physical adsorption there is an appreciable fall, to the extent of about 20 to 35 per cent, in the values for chemisorption.

Second evidence was obtained by studying benzene adsorption isotherms (35°) on 700°-outgassed carbon blacks before as well as after chemisorption of hydroquinone. The isotherms are plotted in Fig. 1. It is interesting to note that the association of hydroquinone with the surface lowers the tendency of carbon blacks to adsorb benzene vapour, particularly at lower relative vapour pressures. It appears that quinonic groups are not as free now to interact with electrons of benzene. This may be due to formation of semiquinone structures on the surface as postulated above.

Fig. 1. Adsorption isotherms of benzene on 700°-outgassed carbon blacks before and after treatment with hydroquinone.

- △—△—△— Mogul-A outgassed at 700°
- ▲—▲—▲— Mogul-A outgassed at 700° (Treated with Hydroquinone)
- Spheron-C outgassed at 700°
- Spheron-C outgassed at 700° (Treated with Hydroquinone)

The carbon containing chemisorbed hydroquinone (0.5 g.) was treated with aqueous sodium sulphite (50 ml of 0.5 M) and refluxed for a couple of hours. An appreciable amount of hydroquinone, being as much as over 70 per cent of the total chemisorbed, re-appeared in the solution. The recovery of chemisorbed hydroquinone on treatment with sodium sulphite is in accord with the work of Lure et al⁴ who showed that loss of hydroquinone on passing the solution through a charcoal bed can be recovered substantially by leaching the bed with a solution of sodium sulphite. It appears that the semiquinone structures formed on the surface get reduced yielding hydroquinone in solution, and, at the same time, probably, reducing the initial surface quinones to surface hydroquinones. Although there was no direct experimental evidence for the conversion of surface quinones to hydroquinones, a distinct fall in pH of the treated carbon from 4.25 to 3.45 was observed. Such

pH changes observed on reducing a carbon containing quinonic oxygen have been attributed⁷ to partial conversion of quinones to hydroquinones.

There is one snag in the mechanism of chemisorption of hydroquinone suggested above. If chemisorption occurs only at quinonic sites, it becomes difficult to explain chemisorption when carbons, outgassed at 1000°, are essentially free of oxygen (cf. Table 2). The treatment of the residual carbons with sodium sulphite in these cases also caused nearly 70-75 per cent recovery of hydroquinone. Since in such cases there could be no formation of semi-quinone structures, it appears quite likely that chemisorption of hydroquinone occurs at the sites vacated by the original quinonic groups and a part of it changes into quinonic structures through oxidation by the presence of air in the bottle containing the suspension. The treatment with sodium sulphite results in the partial reduction of these surface quinones to free hydroquinone which passes into solution.

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